

Expert survey: Mental health in the transition to retirement

13. Jan. 2026

This survey aims to gather expert knowledge to inform the design of a retirement companion, a digital tool to support mental health during the transition from work to retirement.

* Erforderlich

Introduction

This expert survey is part of the **RetirementCompanion** project [1] which is conducted by researchers from the Bern University of Applied Sciences in Switzerland. The project aims to design and develop a digital companion app that supports adults aged 60 and above as they transition from working life to retirement, with a special focus on mental health support during this shift. This survey gathers expert perspectives to inform the app's design requirements, identify potential risks to avoid, and guide strategies for effective integration and sustained use. Your input will help us create a digital solution that truly supports people during this transition.

By sending your answers you agree with the anonymized analysis of your answers.

This expert survey contains 17 questions and takes about 20 minutes to complete. The survey will be open until November 30, 2025.

If you have questions or are interested in the results, feel free to contact Kerstin Denecke, kerstin.denecke@bfh.ch

[1] Project website: RetirementCompanion. Retrieved on October 28, 2025 from <https://www.bfh.ch/en/research/research-projects/2025-630-249-824/>

Understanding the retirement transition and mental health

1. What are the most common psychological and emotional challenges you see in people during the transition from working life to retirement?

2. Which factors most strongly influence mental health during this transition? *

- Loss of work identity and purpose
- Changes in social relationships
- Lack of daily structure and routine
- Financial instability
- Physical health decline
- Family changes
- Isolation and loneliness
- Sonstiges

3. Which groups of workers are most vulnerable to mental health challenges during the transition from work to retirement (e.g., managers, academics, or those in physically demanding jobs)?

4. Which opportunities commonly emerge from the transition from working life to retirement?

5. Are there any other important mental health considerations during the transition from work to retirement not addressed above?

Design and functionalities of the digital companion app

6. What areas should a digital companion address to support users during the transition from working life to retirement?

7. How important is it to address the following dimensions in the digital companion (5-item scale)? *

	Unimportant	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important
Emotional self-regulation	<input type="radio"/>				
Maintaining social connections	<input type="radio"/>				
Coping with loss of identity and purpose	<input type="radio"/>				
Building daily structure and routines	<input type="radio"/>				
Promoting physical health habits	<input type="radio"/>				
Enabling access to professional support	<input type="radio"/>				

Enabling access to financial guidance	<input type="radio"/>				
Sleep and stress management	<input type="radio"/>				

8. Are there other dimensions that need to be addressed in a digital retirement companion?

9. Which features would be most effective in supporting mental health during the transition from work to retirement? *

- Self-reflection or journaling
- Mood tracking and wellbeing monitoring
- Guided exercises (e.g., relaxation, mindfulness)
- Peer community and discussion forum
- Educational materials on mental health and retirement
- Goal-setting or habit-building tools
- Sonstiges

10. What aspects of the app's design or content should be avoided to prevent negative or unsafe effects for this user group?

Integration into users' daily lives and sustained use of the app

11. How should a retirement companion be introduced to the users? *

- Recommended by clinicians or therapists
- Recommended by human resources
- Recommended by the primary care provider
- Recommended by community centers or non-governmental organizations (NGOs)
- Sonstiges

12. Which barriers do you foresee that might prevent persons from engaging with a digital retirement companion?

13. How can a retirement companion best promote ongoing engagement and prevent drop-off in usage?

Background and expertise

14. What is your professional background? *

- Clinical psychologist
- Psychiatrist
- Psychotherapist
- Social worker
- Gerontologist
- Primary care physician
- Human Resources (HR)
- Sonstiges

15. How many years of working experience do you have ? *

- 0-5 years
- 5-10 years
- 10-15 years
- 15-20 years
- 20+ years

16. Primary work settings: *

- Public sector
- Private sector
- Community services
- Primary care
- Academia
- Sonstiges

17. Continent where you are currently working: *

- Africa
- Asia
- Europe
- Australia and Oceania
- North America
- South America

Final section

Thank you very much for your participation!

Your input is extremely valuable for developing a useful digital companion app for the retirement transition. We will make sure to integrate your suggestions throughout the design and development process.

If you have any questions, please feel free to contact the research team directly: kerstin.denecke@bfh.ch

Dieser Inhalt wurde von Microsoft weder erstellt noch gebilligt. Die von Ihnen übermittelten Daten werden an den Formulareigentümer gesendet.

 Microsoft Forms